

Clinical Study of Thrombocytopenia in Dengue Fever

DR SHANKARAAPP R S

Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Sree Siddartha Medical College, Tumakuru, Karnataka

ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Dengue is a mosquito-borne viral disease by Flaviviridae family causing wide spectrum of disease ranging from subclinical disease, severe flu-like symptoms to severe dengue associated with severe bleeding, organ impairment and/or plasma leakage with higher risk of death when not managed appropriately. WHO classifies as DF/ DHF/DSS earlier, at present as Dengue (with or without warning signs) and Severe Dengue. The virus may be detected by NS1 antigen and by ELISA IgM IgG antibodies. Thrombocytopenia is one of the laboratory parameter in grading severity, a study is planned during an epidemic in south Karnataka region which would have a substantial impact on management by reducing morbidity and mortality associated with dengue.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES: To correlate warning signs, laboratory parameters in different age groups, sex, with severity of thrombocytopenia with management.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: Prospective observational study conducted at south Karnataka for patients more than 15 years with Dengue NS1 Antigen positive or IgM/IgG positive and Platelet count less than 1, 50,000 per dl. Detailed clinical history and detailed physical examination was recorded in a prescribed preform and subjected to Dengue NS1 Antigen, IgM and IgG antibodies, Complete blood count, Random Blood Sugar, Urine analysis, Liver Function tests, Renal Function tests, Abdominal sonography, ECG and managed conservatively. Data was entered in Microsoft Office Excel Sheet 2010 and analyzed.

RESULTS: There are 124 thrombocytopenia, out of which 76 severe, 34 moderate and 14 mild thrombocytopenia, 74 (60%) are NS1 positive and 57 (46%) are IgM positive, 79 males (64%) and 45 females (36%), 49% are in 15-30 age (12% in 15-20, 37% in 21-30) and 20% in 31-40 age, commonest clinical presentations along with fever are Headache 70%, myalgia 68%, nausea and vomiting 41%, arthralgia 27%, warning signs are abdominal pain 18%, bleeding manifestations 6%, restlessness 8%, altered sensorium 4%, bradycardia 26%, hypotension 17%, hepatomegaly 11%, abnormal laboratory parameters are leucopenia in 43%, abnormal renal function tests in 20%, elevated liver enzymes in 35% cases 88%. There are 88% Dengue with warning signs, 24% Severe Dengue with 17% circulatory collapse, 14% renal, 8% hepatic and 4% nervous involvement. Platelet transfusion done only in 27%.

CONCLUSION: Moderate to severe thrombocytopenia in young adults with NS1 / IgM positive is the commonest warning sign followed by abdominal pain, bleeding manifestations, restlessness, altered sensorium, leucopenia, bradycardia, hypotension, polyserositis, abdominal tenderness, hepatomegaly, elevated liver enzymes, hyperbilirubinemia, abnormal renal function tests. Majority require supportive management and may not require platelet transfusion. Early recognition of warning signs and meticulous management can reduce the morbidity and mortality of dengue.

KEY WORDS: Severe Thrombocytopenia, Dengue NS1 Antigen, Severe Dengue, warning signs

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
26 February 2022

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org>

Clinical Study of Thrombocytopenia in Dengue Fever

INTRODUCTION

Thrombocytopenia is the commonest platelet abnormality encountered in clinical practice with variable clinical manifestations. Thrombocytopenia refers to reduction in platelet count below 1.5 lakhs per microliter in peripheral blood. The lifespan of platelet is around 7-10 days and about 10 percent are destroyed each day¹. Thrombocytopenia results from impaired platelet production, accelerated destruction, dilutional or splenic sequestration². Clinicians may encounter many cases of thrombocytopenia with widespread use of automated cell counters and because platelet counts are prone to errors a single platelet count that is lower than normal should be confirmed by a second count and by inspecting the peripheral blood smear. Thrombocytopenia is classified based on platelet count as mild when platelet count is 1.0 to 1.5 lakhs/microliter, moderate when platelet count is 0.5 to 1.0 lakh/microliter and severe when platelet count is less than 0.5 lakh/microliter of blood. Dengue is a mosquito-borne viral disease caused by a virus of the Flaviviridae family (DENV-1, DENV-2, DENV-3 and DENV-4), transmitted by female mosquitoes mainly *Aedes aegypti* to a lesser extent, *Ae. Albopictus* which are also vectors of chikungunya, yellow fever and Zika viruses. Dengue causes a wide spectrum of disease ranging from subclinical disease, severe flu-like symptoms to severe dengue associated with severe bleeding, organ impairment and/or plasma leakage with higher risk of death when not managed appropriately. WHO earlier classifies Dengue as DF/ DHF/DSS³. Dengue Fever (DF) is a patient having fever with two or more of the following: Headache, Retro-orbital pain, Myalgia, Arthralgia, Leucopenia, mild thrombocytopenia. Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF) is one having above signs along with one or more of the following: positive tourniquet test, Thrombocytopenia < 100,000, Hematocrit rise \geq 20%, spontaneous bleeding. Dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS) is one having above signs with circulatory failure weak pulse, hypotension, restlessness or Profound shock with undetectable BP and Pulse³. WHO classifies dengue into 2 major categories⁴: Dengue (with / without warning signs) and Severe Dengue. Dengue fever without warning signs Living in or travel to dengue endemic area presenting with Fever and 2 of the following criteria: Nausea, vomiting, Rash, Aches and pain, positive tourniquet test, Leucopenia, Laboratory confirmed dengue. Dengue fever with warning signs are abdominal pain or tenderness, Persistent vomiting, Clinical fluid accumulation, mucosal.

Bleed, Lethargy, restlessness, Liver enlargement >2cm, Increase in hematocrit with rapid decrease in platelet count⁴. Severe dengue is potentially a fatal complication due to plasma leakage, fluid accumulation, respiratory distress, severe bleeding, or organ impairment which require close observation to avoid complications and risk of death. Haemopoietic system is the earliest and commonly

Affected system with thrombocytopenia being the most common laboratory finding. Possible mechanisms include direct bone marrow suppression by the virus, anti-dengue antibody mediated platelet destruction, effects of cytokine release, peripheral consumption of platelets and Isolated viral replication in the platelet⁵. The virus may be detected by testing NS1 antigen and by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) IgM antibodies appearing 1 week after infection reaching highest at 2 to 4 weeks and remaining detectable for about 3 months and IgG antibody which appear later than IgM remaining for years. The number of dengue cases reported to WHO increased over 8fold over the last two decades, from 505,430 cases in 2000 to over 2.4 million in 2010 and 5.2 million in 2019 with deaths increased from 960 in 2000 to 4032 in 2015. The largest number of dengue cases ever reported globally was in 2019. In India (Karnataka) also number of cases increased from 99913 (5077) with 220 (9) deaths in 2015, to 157315 (16986) cases with 166(13) deaths in 2019⁶. The sub-classification of dengue with or without warning signs is designed to help health practitioners to triage patients for hospital admission, ensuring close observation minimizing the risk of developing severe dengue. As thrombocytopenia is one of the laboratory parameter in grading severity, we commonly see positive dengue serology with thrombocytopenia patients being referred as this is a tertiary care referral center with availability of blood products. Hence it is planned to study other warning signs, laboratory parameters with the severity of thrombocytopenia in dengue fever. This study would have a substantial impact on management by reducing morbidity and mortality associated with dengue, reducing unnecessary burden on patients and by reducing referrals to higher centers.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To study warning signs, laboratory parameters in different age groups, sex, with severity of thrombocytopenia with management.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

It is a prospective observational study conducted for a period of 3 months from November 2019 to January 2020 in the Department of General Medicine, Shridevi institute of medical sciences and research hospital, Tumakuru. All patients admitted with platelet counts less than 1.5 lakh per microliter with laboratory confirmed dengue cases were included in the study. Inclusion criteria: 1. all in patients with Dengue NS1 Antigen positive or IgM/IgG positive. 2. Platelet count less than 1, 50,000 per dl. Exclusion criteria 1. Age less than 15 years. 2. Other causes of thrombocytopenia due to infections other than dengue, megaloblastic anemia, cirrhosis etc. Detailed clinical history and detailed physical examination was recorded in a prescribed proforma including age, sex, symptoms like fever, headache,

Clinical Study of Thrombocytopenia in Dengue Fever

arthralgia, nausea, vomiting, pain abdomen, hematuria, bleeding gums, hematemesis and significant clinical signs like hypotension, tachypnea, heart rate, mucosal bleed, purpuric spots, tourniquet test, tender abdomen, icterus, hepatomegaly, ascites, splenomegaly, were recorded. All patients were subjected to Dengue NS1Antigen, IgM and IgG antibodies, Complete blood count and analyzed for hemoglobin, hematocrit, leukocyte count and platelet count by Automated Analyzer with confirmation by pathologist for thrombocytopenia by peripheral blood smear, Random Blood Sugar, Urine analysis, Malarial parasite, Widal test, Liver Function tests, Renal Function tests, Abdominal sonography, Chest radiography, ECG, Echocardiography.

Patients were managed conservatively with fluid supplementation and platelet transfusion whenever required. Data was entered in Microsoft Office Excel Sheet 2010 and analyzed the results.

RESULTS

During the study period 150 patients are serologically positive for Dengue. Among them 124 had thrombocytopenia, platelet count less than 150000.76 had severe (3300 being lowest in our study with 46 having 10000 to 30000 and 37 having 30000 to 50000), 34 had had moderate, and 14 had mild thrombocytopenia (Table No 1).

Table 1. Severity of thrombocytopenia

PLATELET COUNT	NO.OF PATIENTS(124)	PERCENTAGE
100000 -150000 (MILD)	14	11.3%
50000 - 100000 (MODERATE)	34	27.4%
<50000 (SEVERE)	76	61.3%
<10000	01	
10000 - 20000	26	
20000 - 30000	20	
30000 - 40000	17	
40000 - 50000	12	

Among 124, 74(60%) are NS1 positive, 57(46%) are IgM positive, 44 (35%) are IgG positive, 27 (21%) are NS1 and

IgM positive, 16(12%) are NS1 and IgG positive, 12(10%) are NS1,IgG,IgM positive(Table 2).

Table 2. Dengue serology report of patients

Dengue serology	No. of patients	percentage
NS1 antigen	74	60%
IgM Dengue	57	46%
Ig G Dengue	44	35%
NS1 antigen + IgM Dengue	27	21%
NS1 antigen + IgG Dengue	16	12%
NS1 antigen+ IgM Dengue + IgG Dengue	12	10%

Among 124 there were 79 males (64%) with 51 severe, 19 moderate,9 mildthrombocytopenia and 45 females (36%)

with 25 severe, 15 moderate,5 mildthrombocytopenia(Table 3).

Table 3. Gender distribution of patients

SEX	MALE	FEMALE
MILD THROMBOCYTOPENIA	09	05
MODERATE THROMBOCYTOPENIA	19	15
SEVERE THROMBOCYTOPENIA	51	25
TOTAL PATIENTS	79 64%	45 36%

There were patients from 15 to 70 years of age with highest incidence in the age group of 15-30 years in 60 cases followed by 25 cases 31-40 years, 22 in 41- 50 and 17 in 51-

70 years.Majority (69%) are in 15 to 40 years with 36% in 21-30, 20% in 31-40,18% in 41-50, only 5% in >60 years(Table No 4).

Clinical Study of Thrombocytopenia in Dengue Fever

Table 4. Age distribution of patients

AGE GROUP	MILD	MODERATE	SEVERE	TOTAL
15 TO 20 YEARS	03	03	09	15 (12%)
21 TO 30 YEARS	04	13	28	45 (37%)
31 TO 40 YEARS	04	06	15	25(20%)
41 TO 50 YEARS	00	08	14	22(18%)
51 TO 60 YEARS	01	03	06	10(08%)
61 TO 70 YEARS	02	01	04	07(05%)
TOTAL CASES	14	34	76	124

The commonest clinical presentation in the study is fever in all followed by Headache in 87, myalgia in 85, nausea and vomiting in 52, arthralgia in 34 patients. The commonest warning signs are abdominal pain in 22, bleeding

manifestations in 8, restlessness in 10, altered sensorium in 5 cases. The commonest clinical signs are bradycardia in 33, hypotension in 22, hepatomegaly in 14 cases. (Table No 5).

Table 5. Commonest clinical manifestations with warning signs

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS	TOTAL CASES (124)	SEVERE (76) THROMBOCYTOPENIA
HEADACHE	87(70%)	55 (72%)
MYALGIA	85(68%)	50(65%)
NAUSEA/VOMITING	52(41%)	32(42%)
ARTHRALGIA	34(27%)	21(27%)
BLEEDING MANIFESTATION	08(06%)	06(8%)
ABDOMINAL PAIN	22(18%)	14(18%)
RESTLESSNESS	10(8%)	07(9%)
BRADYCARDIA	33(26%)	26(34%)
HYPOTENSION	22(17%)	15(20%)
HEPATOMEGALY	14(11%)	11(14%)
ALTERED SENSORIUM	05(4%)	05 (6%)

The commonest abnormal laboratory parameters observed are leucopenia in 53, hematocrit more than 45 in 18,

abnormal renal function tests in 25, elevated liver enzymes in 36 and hyperbilirubinemia in 10 cases. (Table No 6).

Table 6. Commonest Abnormal Laboratory Parameters

LABORATORY PARAMETERS	TOTAL (124)	SEVERE (76)
LEUCOPENIA	53(43%)	33 (43%)
HAEMATOCRIT	18(15%)	17(22%)
RENAL FUNCTION TESTS	25(20%)	15(20%)
ELEVATED LIVER ENZYME	36(29%)	27(35%)
HYPERBILIRUBINAEMIA	10(08%)	08 (11%)

There are 124 cases of Dengue Fever out of which 88 are graded as DHF and 22 as DSS. There are 110 Dengue Fever with warning signs having platelet count of less than

1 lakh. There are 30 Severe Dengue out of which 22 circulatory collapse, 5 neurological, 10 hepatic and 18 renal damage. (Table No 7).

Table 7.

GRADING OF DENGUE	NO. PATIENTS
Dengue Fever	124
Dengue with warning signs	110
Severe Dengue	30
Dengue Haemorrhagic Fever	88
Dengue Shock Syndrome	22

Clinical Study of Thrombocytopenia in Dengue Fever

Platelet transfusion done in 34 cases of which 29 are NS1 /IGM positive.

There was no mortality in the study.

DISCUSSION

During our study majority 88.7% had platelet count of less than 100000/dl, compared to 86% by Shankarappa⁷ in a study of thrombocytopenia, 74% by Naveen⁸ and 77.2% by Girish⁹ in study of dengue fever from same area, 77.2% by Vidyadarani¹¹ from Telangana. 11.3% had mild, 27.4% had moderate and 61.3% had severe thrombocytopenia compared to 61% by Vidyadarani¹¹. During our study 60% NS1 positive, 46% IgM positive, 21% both NS1 & IgM positive compared to 70% NS1 positive, 7% IgM positive, 11% both NS1 & IgM positive by Girish⁹, 66.9% NS1 positive, 33.1% NS1 & IgM positive by Wayez A¹², 33% NS1 positive, 63% IgM positive by Shivraj Nagnath Kanthikar¹⁰, 49% NS1 positive, 5% IgM positive, 3% NS1 & IgM by Vidyadarani¹¹, 51% NS1 positive by Patta Apparao¹³. During our study 64% male 36% female compared to 56% male 44% female by Naveen⁸, 59% male 41% female by Girish⁹, 61.5% males 38.5% females by Vidyadarani¹¹, 55% male 45% female by Wayez A¹², 53% male 47% female by Shwetha JH¹⁴. During our study 49% are in 15-30 age (12% in 15-20, 37% in 21-30), 20% in 31-40 age compared to 43.52% in 15-30 by Vidyadarani¹¹, 66% in 15-30 by Wayez A¹², 68% in 15-40 by Naveen⁸. The commonest clinical presentations along with fever in the study are Headache 70%, myalgia 68%, nausea and vomiting 41%, arthralgia 27% compared to headache 68% myalgia 72%, nausea and vomiting 31%, arthralgia 43% by Naveen⁸, headache 70%, arthralgia 45% by Girish⁹. There is no difference among severity of thrombocytopenia. The commonest warning signs are abdominal pain in 18%, bleeding manifestations in 6%, restlessness in 8%, bradycardia in 26%, hypotension in 17%, hepatomegaly in 11% altered sensorium in 4%. Bleeding manifestations, bradycardia, hypotension, hepatomegaly are more common in severe thrombocytopenia. Bleeding manifestations are 13.1% by Wayez A¹², 8% by Girish⁹. The commonest abnormal laboratory parameters observed are leucopenia in 43%, abnormal renal function tests in 20%, elevated liver enzymes in 35% cases compared to leucopenia in 27%, abnormal renal function tests in 27%, elevated liver enzymes in 24.5% by Wayez A¹². There are 88% Dengue with warning signs, 24% Severe Dengue with 17% circulatory collapse, 14% renal, 8% hepatic and 4% neural damage as narrated by Nataraj Gangasiddaiah¹⁵. Platelet transfusion done only in 27%.

CONCLUSION

Thrombocytopenia is one of the commonest warning signs in dengue fever specially moderate to severe thrombocytopenia in young adults who are serologically NS1 / IgM positive

followed by abdominal pain, bleeding manifestations, restlessness, altered sensorium, leucopenia. Cardiovascular warning signs like bradycardia, hypotension, polyserositis, Hepatic warning signs like abdominal tenderness, hepatomegaly, elevated liver enzymes, hyperbilirubinemia, Renal warning signs like abnormal renal function tests and Neurological warning signs like altered sensorium are commonly observed. Dengue fever with thrombocytopenia is one of the most common important major public problem in India where cyclic epidemics are becoming more frequent. Majority require supportive management and may not require platelet transfusion. Most of the cases can be managed at the local hospital with close monitoring of warning signs and laboratory parameters. Early recognition of warning signs and meticulous management can reduce the morbidity and mortality of dengue.

REFERENCES

- I. API Textbook of Medicine; Sandhya A Kamath; Siddarth N Shah; YP Munjal; 2019; edition ELEVEN: VOLUME 1; Chapter 16; Platelet disorders, prantar Chakrabarti, page 973.
- II. Jameson, Fauci, Kasper, Hauser, Longo, Loscalzo. Disorders of platelets and vessel wall. Section 3. Chapter 111, In: Harrison principles of internal medicine, 20th Ed. vol. 1. 2018. pp 822.
- III. DENGUE .Guidelines for diagnosis, treatment, prevention and control, 2nd Edition, World Health Organization, Geneva 2009; 1-144.
- IV. <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/dengue-and-severe-dengue> world health organisation Dengue and severe dengue, 19 May 2021.
- V. Sanyaolu A, Okorie C, Badaru O, Adetona K, Ahmed M et al. (2017) Global Epidemiology of Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever: An Update. Review Article 5(6): 00179. DOI: 10.15406/jhvr.2017.05.00179.
- VI. National vector borne disease, at: https://www.karnataka.gov.in/hfw/nhm/pages/ndcp_cd_nvbdcp.aspx. Accessed on 21 December 2017.
- VII. Dr Shankarappa R S Dr Naveen K: Clinical Study of Thrombocytopenia; JMSCR Vol|08|Issue01|Page 362-367|January 2020.
- VIII. K Naveen, R S Shankarappa, S Vathsala: Study of clinico-haematological profile in dengue fever - A prospective study. MedPulse International Journal of Medicine. July 2020; 15(1): 09-14.
- IX. Girish Babu RJ, Madhuri K: A Clinico-microbiological study of dengue fever cases at Sri Siddhartha medical college and hospital, Tumkur. Indian J Microbiol Res 2016; 3(2): 209-212.
- X. Shivraj Nagnath Kanthikar, Varsha Tukaram Kalshetti: Correlation of thrombocytopenia and serological markers in early diagnosis of dengue

Clinical Study of Thrombocytopenia in Dengue Fever

infection with special reference to NS1 antigen, Indian Journal of Pathology and Oncology, July-September 2016;3(3);437-439.

- XI. Vidyadhara Rani P, Naveen Kumar S. Evaluation of thrombocytopenia in dengue infection along with seasonal variation. IAIM, 2018; 5(2): 57-63.
- XII. Wayez A, Zafar L, Aijaz M, Afroz N (2020) Study of platelet indices in dengue fever with thrombocytopenia and correlation of immature platelet fraction (IPF) with platelet recovery. Arch Hematol Case Rep Rev 5(1): 001-005. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17352/ahcrr.000021>
- XIII. PattaApparao, D.K.V. Prasad and Lavanya, S.V. 2018. Seasonal, Serological Markers and Platelet Count Association with Dengue Fever. Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci. 7(10): 2513-2517.
- XIV. Shwetha JH1, Ashoka A2, Shashikala P Evaluation of platelet count as a predictive parameter in pediatric patients with dengue fever in a tertiary care center in Davangere Indian Journal of Pathology and Oncology, January-March 2017;4(1):77-79
- XV. NatarajGangasiddaiah, Nagaraj Nanjundaiah Dengue fever: atypical manifestation International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences 1 October-December 2014 Vol 2 Issue 4 Page 1804